

PROBLEMS IN STANDARDIZATION OF PRODUCTS AND THEIR ANALYSIS AS A PROBLEM

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Annotation

The potential of the standard in various spheres of renewed life occupies a special place in society, the state, especially in the field of ecological geology. As a result of the analysis of foreign literature, various aspects of standards are highlighted, the historical goal of standardizing modern society and turning it into a science, taking into account their functional purpose, teleological, impact-impressive, etc., Their role. and place. It is argued that standardization is at the heart of change in science and technology.

Key words: standardization, standard, goal of standardization, retrospective, international standardization, international organizations, functions of standardization, principles of standardization.

Аннотация

Потенциал стандарта в различных сферах обновленной жизни занимает особое место в обществе, государстве, особенно в области экологической геологии. В результате анализа зарубежной литературы выделены различные аспекты стандартов, историческая цель стандартизации современного общества и превращения его в науку с учетом их функционального назначения, телеологического, импактно-импрессивного и т. д., их роль и место. Утверждается, что стандартизация лежит в основе изменений в науке и технике.

Ключевые слова: стандартизация, стандарт, цель стандартизации, ретроспектива, международная стандартизация, международные организации, функции стандартизации, принципы стандартизации.

Introduction

At the present stage of human existence, the problem of preserving and using the knowledge gained in the course of history is urgent.

Modern processes such as globalization, integration and regionalization are interconnected, and standardization is the basis of structures such as economics, culture, science and politics that facilitate integration. Based on this, international relations are developing at a faster pace.

At the present stage of development of society, environmental standards are becoming one of the requirements. It is increasingly seen as a means of regulating defense relationships. Use of nature and natural resources.

This trend requires adherence to use standards that warn of the increasing environmental impact of the industry and the dwindling of mineral reserves.

All of the above realizes the potential. This necessitates an understanding of standards and conditions, especially the environment, in various spheres of society. So understanding the standard is at least striving for unity. This block requires an objective and

systematic relationship in which the individual parts are compatible with each other. Balanced and proportional, they complement each other.

In an ontological sense, standards are the optimal benefit to a society based on practical experience and achievements based on science, technology and generalized results. Etymologically, the term "standard" refers to a pattern. This is a document that contains events about size, shape, quality, as well as related information [1]. That is, a standard (English Standard - norm) is considered a standard, a sample and is taken as a basis. This means that any model can be used to test other objects or properties with it [2].

The standard is a normative document and approved by the competent authority. Defines rules, properties or general provisions. The purpose of this document is to achieve the best order level in a specific area [3]. Standards are developed both for material products (products, samples of substances) and for norms, rules and requirements in various fields.

There are standardized norms that define, legislate, organize and apply the concept of "standard", rules, works, products, services, etc. They represent a huge economic, social and scientific content of standardization.

Usually standardization has many teleological dominants: it provides security, products, works, services for the environment, life, health and property of citizens; technical and data compatibility, as well as product compatibility; uniformity of measurements: saving resources, increasing energy efficiency and reducing energy and material consumption of products, works and services; safety of business entities, taking into account the risk of natural and man-made disasters and other emergencies.

A.P. According to Batalova, standardization is a normative way to ensure product quality, the process of defining and applying these rules. This benefits from the regulation of the industry and the requirements of economy and safety with the participation of all interested parties, in particular, the observance of functional conditions to achieve a general maximum [4, 5].

If you study historical hindsight, you may notice that some peoples began using standardized products centuries ago. Even in ancient Egypt, durable bricks of the "standard" size were used for construction; at the same time, special officials were in charge of controlling the size of the bricks. Magnificent monuments of ancient Greek architecture, famous temples are assembled from "standard" parts. The ancient Romans used the principles of standardization in the construction of water pipes (water pipes) - their pipes were the same and constant size. In the Middle Ages, with the development of crafts and mass production, more and more methods of standardization began to be applied. Thus, uniform requirements have been established for raw materials used in the textile industry, the same dimensions of the width of the fabric, the amount of yarn based on it.

In 1785, the French engineer Leblanc created 50 weapons, each with significant quality characteristics. In the second half of the 19th century, standardization work was carried out in almost all industrial enterprises.

Managed to rationalize the manufactured products through standardization at the plant. Standardization has been developed, first of all, within individual firms, individual enterprises. However, later, with the development of the social division of labor and the growth of international trade, national and international standardization began to gain in importance.

In 1891, the standard (in inches) was introduced in England, and then in other countries, and later it was replaced by meter threads in most countries. In 1846 Germany merged railroad tracks and couplings; In 1869, a guide was published here for the first time with the dimensions of standard profiles. In 1870, standard sizes were established in a number of European countries. The first results of these national and international results were that standardization was of great practical importance for the development of productive forces [6].

You should pay attention to the process of setting the units of measurement: for example, "elbow" corresponded to the length of the bar of Henry I; The unit of measure for length, which was widely used in many countries, was "foot", corresponding to the length of Charlemagne's feet. However, the search for more reasonable units of measurement continues unabated. Thus, already in 1790 in France, together they created a unit of equal length "meter". Participation in the International Metric Convention In 1875, Paris agreed to accept "meter" as the unit of length.

The creation of the Metric Convention and the International Bureau of Weights and Measures was an important step in the development of science and technology. In the late 19th - early 20th centuries, great strides were made in the concentration of technology, industry and production. In this regard, a desire arose to organize national standardization in the most developed countries. In most cases, this ended with the creation of national standards organizations. Thus, in 1901, a Committee on Standards was formed in Great Britain, the main task of which was to help strengthen the economic strength of the British Empire by developing and implementing standards for raw materials, industrial products and military equipment.

In this respect, it is not surprising that several national standards organizations were formed during the First World War, for example, the Netherlands (1916), Germany (1917), France, Switzerland and the United States (1918).

With the development of monopoly capitalism, standardization began to develop at the international level. The constant expansion of international trade and the need for closer cooperation in science and technology led to the creation of the International Association for Standardization. In 1943, as part of the institutionalization process of the United Nations, a Standardization Coordination Committee was established with offices in London and New York.

In 1946, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) covered 33 countries. Currently ISO is one of the largest international technical organizations (its members are 164 countries) [8].

Standardization is carried out at different levels:

- International standardization, participation in which is open to specialized agencies of all countries.
- development or revision of national standards;
- Interregional standardization, participation in which is open only to the relevant authorities of the countries of one geographic or economic region of the world;
- national standardization is standardization within one state;
- organization standards, industry standards, enterprise standards, company standards, etc.

Like other disciplines, standardization activities are based on certain rules - principles. The principles of standardization reflect the basic laws of the process of developing a standard, substantiate its necessity in managing the national economy, and determine the conditions for effective implementation and directions of development [9].

At the same time, it is possible to single out the principles that reflect the international aspect of standardization, as well as its functional and dynamic features:

1. application of an international standard as a basis, development of a national standard; standardization of sustainability;
2. the effectiveness of standardization;
3. The principle of harmonization.

Standardization functions include the following. Corresponds to the tasks of other disciplines, but their essence is seen here from a different angle:

- ordering function - associated with the elimination, simplification and limitation of an unjustified variety of objects;

- protective (social) function - ensuring the safety of consumers of products (services);

- producers and the state unite the efforts of mankind to protect nature from the anthropogenic impact of civilization, to protect animals.

- resource-saving function - due to the limited material, energy, labor and natural resources;

- rule-making function - is reflected in the formation of norms and requirements (rules, parameter values, conditions for implementation), etc.

The goals of standardization are social and economic development, fostering integration, improving the quality of life, improving the quality of products and services provided, and much more. The main tasks of standardization are to ensure mutual understanding between developers, manufacturers, suppliers and consumers (customers); establishment of optimal requirements for the range and quality of products in the interests of the consumer and the state, including ensuring its safety for the environment, life, health and property; setting compatibility requirements (design, electrical, electromagnetic, information, software, etc.), as well as product interchangeability; normative and technical support for control (testing, analysis, measurements), certification and product quality assessment; creation and maintenance of systems for classification and coding of technical and economic information; interstate and state socio-economic and scientific-technical programs (projects) and infrastructure complexes (transport, communications, defense, security) [10]. Environment, environmental control, public safety, etc.); use of resources to ensure sustainability, etc.

The standardization is factual (reflecting some of the historical characteristics and rules of society, for example, it is generally accepted that you should eat three times a day: breakfast in the morning, lunch in the afternoon and dinner in the evening.) Current regulations.

Conclusion

With increasing economic development, international standardization is gaining in importance. Although international standards do not have a binding status for everyone, and any country in the world has the right to apply or not to apply them, the export of products largely depends on the level of product standardization. Manufacturers strive to ensure high

competitiveness and use the standards of international organizations in their activities. This makes a significant contribution to improving product quality.

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